

Splitting Water into Hydrogen and Oxygen using Lasers.

Water molecule is composed by two atoms of hydrogen and one of oxygen which are bound together. Can we use special lasers to split the two compounds of water with the purpose of mass producing liquid hydrogen and oxygen to use it as a fuel in the future?

Using this splitting process we can mass produce new types of fuels like liquid hydrogen and oxygen to be used in the automobile and other vehicle's industries thus eliminating the need of gasoline.

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